

Research project

Errors in Finnish surnames' machine translation

Machine translation is widely used not only by professional translators, but regular people as well on a nearly everyday basis. On many occasions professional translators use machine translation and post-editing instead of translating from scratch. Regular users use free machine translation engines when using social media or on other occasions. In both cases, the quality of machine translation is of increasing importance.

There is a lot of research focusing on machine translation engine output quality. However, qualitative analysis of machine translation error types is not as common. In addition to that, research tends to focus on the bigger European languages with smaller ones like Finnish receiving less attention (Koponen & Salmi, 2017: 138), for which a lot of reference data can be found. Finnish is a language with characteristics that might create quality difficulties for machine translation engines (ibid).

These are the reasons why the focus of my research project is on Finnish language machine translation. My plan is to translate strings of texts from Finnish to English using two free of charge machine translation engines: Google Translate and DeepL. Google Translate and DeepL are one of the most common free machine translation engines used by internet users on a daily basis. Both translation engines represent neural machine translation.

My research questions are as follows:

- Research question: What kind of errors occur in the process of machine translating Finnish surnames?
- What kinds of surnames does machine translation engines translate well and what kinds does it struggle with?
- Are there any noticeable differences between the two different machine translators?

Data cleaning and processing

For my dataset I chose to use the Finnish language corpus of Yle (Finnish National Broadcaster) texts. This corpus is open-to-all corpus that provides a list of separate strings of text published in a certain section, such as sports, culture and entertainment. Corpus does not support extended context. Open-to-all Yle corpus has eleven sections: "Yle Asia", "Yle Elävä arkisto", "Yle Kulttuuri ja viihde", "Yle Sapmi", "Yle Selkouutiset", "Yle Urheilu", "Yle Uutiset", "Yle Uutiset – lyhyet", "Yle Uutisluokka", "Yle Viestintä", "YleX", "Yleisradion Eläkesäätiö" and "yle-aihe". Out of these I chose to use five: "Yle Asia", "Yle Elävä arkisto", "Yle

Kulttuuri ja viihde”, “Yle Urheilu” and “Yle Uutiset” (eng.: “Yle Affairs”, “Yle Living Archive”, “Yle Culture and Entertainment”, “Yle Sports” and “Yle News” respectively).

I focused on searching for two-part names using the <https://korp.csc.fi/> advanced search option. That immediately proved to be challenging as the search returned personal names of all origin, not only Finnish. As there was no section dedicated to the national news (a section I believed would contain the biggest number of Finnish surnames), I had to choose those that upon short analysis seemed to contain the most Finnish surnames. Except for sports section that contained a lot of foreign names, the other four had a high amount of Finnish personal names. I added sport section with hope that it would provide a higher variety of surnames.

As mentioned before, I used <https://korp.csc.fi/> interface to accumulate my data. Korp interface allows downloading the maximum 1000 strings of KWIC search. Although, Korp API allows downloading a much bigger amount of data, after a long consideration I deemed that 1000 strings per each section would be enough for this project, as I would have to analyze the translated output manually and handling larger amount of data might make it too time consuming. Thus, I downloaded 5000 strings (1000 per one section) using the following CQP search:

```
cqp=[msd = ".*SUBCAT_Prop.*" & deprel = "name" & _.text_publisher = "XXX"]
```

XXX must be replaced with one of the section titles, for example “Yle Asia”. I downloaded the results of KWIC search in “SENTENCES_XSL” format, that returned not only the string but also such information as text publisher, text datetime, text url and so on. It also provided lemmatized string. After downloading search results of all five sections separately I started cleaning my data.

I used Excel “Remove duplicates” command and collectively deleted 2019 repeating strings. After that I manually checked and deleted all strings that were:

- in English, instead of Finnish (f. e.: “A concise guide to natural childbirth - Janet Balaskas”)
- in Swedish, instead of Finnish (f. e.: “Studeranden från Sibelius-Akademin framför en kavalkad och RSO & Sakari Oramo uppför Stravinskijns Våroffer .”)
- containing only non-Finnish surnames (f. e.: “Tytöt ovat ihania ja tärkeitä prinsessoja, Raisa Cacciatore hymyilee.”)
- containing two-part names that are not surnames (f. e.: “Tällä hetkellä parhaan ekovalikoiman tarjoaa yllättäen ruotsalainen Hennes & Mauritz .”)
- marked incorrectly as containing names (f. e.: “Hiilarivallankumous maata viljelemällä ”)

Thus, a further 953 strings were deleted. After that, all five separate files were joined into one string list and another "Remove duplicates" command was run, resulting in final total of 1174 non-repeating strings ready to be translated.

I saved the list of strings into a .scv file and used the following code to translate it into English with DeepL:

```
import deepl
import pandas as pd

"""def translate(text):
    auth_key = "b8bc35e9-dff0-aefb-6ac4-4918b7c0a28f:fx"
    text = text.read()
    translator = deepl.Translator(auth_key)
    result = translator.translate_text(text, source_lang = "FI", target_lang="EN-US")
    translated_text = result.text
    return translated_text"""

#def main():
    auth_key = "b8bc35e9-dff0-aefb-6ac4-4918b7c0a28f:fx"
    translator = deepl.Translator(auth_key)
    df = pd.read_csv("Surname Dataset_Cleaned.csv")
    df["target"] = df["text"].apply(lambda x: translator.translate_text(x, source_lang =
"FI", target_lang="EN-US") if type(x) == str else x)
    print(df.head())
    df.to_csv("results/test_translation_df.csv")

    #if __name__ == "__main__":
    #    main()
```

I translated strings into US variant, for no other reason that, in my opinion, US variant of English is much more familiar for most internet users, in comparison to other variants. I was not able to make Google Translate API work, so I ended up translating the text using the usual Google Translate interface. It was a bit laborious, but in the end worked fine, as the translation output was easy to copy and paste to excel, so it ended up perfectly aligning with source strings. It is unclear which English variant does Google Translate use.

Results

After aligning source text and translation from both engines, I started checking the translation. First, I compared translation by Google Translate to source text, and then the translation by DeepL. Afterwards, I compared the errors found in each translation engine output to double check, and in some cases I found some errors I missed during the first check. Number of errors can be seen in the table below.

Translation error in both engines	Translation error only in DeepL	Translation error only in Google Translate
29	14	22

Table 1. Number of translation errors by machine translation engines.

Google Translate made slightly more mistakes (51 total mistake) than DeepL (43 total mistakes). Most of mistakes happened to both machine translation engines when translating the same surnames in the same

string, however that does not mean that the mistakes were identical. For example, string "Miksi Heikki Pellistä rakastetaan ?" was translated by Google Translate as: "Why is Heikki Pellis loved?", and by DeepL as: "Why is Heikki Pell loved ?". And in other times, while both translation engines made a mistake in the same string it concerned a different surname. For example, a following string: " Sanna Santahuhdalta , Elisa Girsiltä ja Marjut Saloselta onnistuvat niin täyte- kuin kuivakakutkin käden käänteessä ." was translated by Google Translate as: "Sanna Santahuhta, Elisa Girsi and Marjut Salose can make both filled and dry cakes in the blink of an eye." and by DeepL as: "Sanna Santahuhuda , Elisa Girsi and Marjut Salonen make both filling and dry cakes in no time at all." Such errors were marked as separate.

Next, I identified all the surnames that had errors in them after translating them to English. Two-part surnames like *Korhonen-Yrjänheikki* or *Jortikka-Laitinen* were considered as separate surnames (*Korhonen*, *Yrjänheikki* and *Jortikka*, *Laitinen*, respectively) for the sake of simplicity. The part that included an error was included in the list as a separate surname. All surnames can be found in the following table in order of the biggest number of appearances to lowest:

Surname	Number of appearance	Number of errors in DeepL	Number of errors in Google Translate.
Pellinen	13	4	4
Salonen	11	0	1
Koskinen	10	1	1
Kortekangas	9	5	7
Nurmi	8	0	1
Pimiä	7	1	2
Pihlaja	7	1	0
Laitinen	7	0	2
Pyykkö	6	4	4
Kalmari	6	1	1
Puustinen	6	0	2
Melin	5	1	1
Kivistö	5	1	0
Pirinen	5	0	2
Kyllönen	4	1	1
Nieminen	4	0	1
Kakko	4	0	1
Valjakka	3	1	1
Mäkinen	3	1	1
Ruutu	3	1	1
Jumppanen	3	1	1
Rissanen	3	0	1
Tonteri	2	1	1
Santahuhta	2	1	0
Summanen	2	1	0
Oksa	2	1	0
Harakka	2	0	1
Ahokas	2	0	1

Nurmelin	2	0	1
Holvas	1	1	1
Välkki	1	1	1
Kivinimi	1	1	1
Sirkiä	1	1	1
Komsi	1	1	1
Raanta	1	1	1
Tarkki	1	1	1
Vilkkö	1	1	1
Pylkkänen	1	1	0
Haataja	1	1	0
Säteri	1	1	0
Ilmonen	1	1	0
Haaparanta	1	1	0
Jauhiainen	1	1	0
Yrjänheikki	1	1	0
Myllärinen	1	0	1
Männikkö	1	0	1
Pulkkis	1	0	1
Hentunen	1	0	1
Hyypiä	1	0	1

Table 2. 49 surnames which translations contained errors, in order of number of appearances in dataset.

Surname that caused most of the errors in both machine translation engines is *Kortekangas* with 5 errors in DeepL and 7 errors in Google Translate with translations such as, *Kortekangaa*, *Kortekanaka*, *Kortekanka*, the latter being the most common. *Pyykkö* and *Pellinen* seemed to also cause problems for machine translation engines, with *Pyykkö* causing 4 errors on both of translation engines, and *Pellinen* causing 4 errors on DeepL and on Google Translate despite being the most common surname in the list.

Some types of surnames caused more errors in translations than others. As can be seen in Table 3 most of errors in Google Translate can be attributed to three groups of surnames:

- ends in *-nen*: *Pellinen*, *Salonen*, *Koskinen* (19 errors)
- ends in *-kk + vowel*: *Pyykkö*, *Valjakka*, *Välkki* (11 errors)
- ends in *vowel + s*: *Kortekangas*, *Holvas*, *Pulkkis* (10 errors)

All errors	-nen	-iä	-kk + V	-l/s	-ki	other
in GT	19	4	11	10	5	4
in DL	12	2	9	6	5	9

Table 3. Surnames with most errors grouped according to their endings.

Similar results also appear when analyzing errors made by Deep L, with most errors in *-nen* group (12), second most in *-kk + vowel* group (9) and *vowel + s* group (6 errors).

Next, I wanted to look at the source text to find out what can possibly cause errors occurring. Finnish is highly inflectional language and there is a high chance that that is the reason for translation errors. I was interested to find out which Finnish case declinations possibly cause most problems.

Cases	Google Translate errors	DeepL errors
Ablative	4	3
Accusative	3	4
Adessive	2	3
Allative	4	5
Genitive	27	23
Nominative	5	2
Partitive	5	4

Table 4. Number of errors per case in which surnames appear in source text

Genitive case has overwhelmingly the highest number of errors with 27 errors for Google Translate and 23 for Deep L. It is an interesting finding, as all of the other cases excluding Nominative and Partitive (in most cases) cause consonant gradation, example of which can be seen in Table 5 bellow.

Nominative	Ablative	Accusative	Adessive	Allative	Genitive	Partitive
Kortekangas	Kortekankaalta	Kortekankaan	Kortekankaalla	Kortekankaalle	Kortekankaan	Kortekangasta
Pellinen	Pelliseltä	Pellisen	Pellisellä	Pelliselle	Pellisen	Pellistä
Pyykkö	Pyyköltä	Pyykön	Pyyköllä	Pyykölle	Pyykön	Pyykköä

Table 5. Consonant gradation in some of the Finnish noun cases.

The possible explanation for overrepresentation of errors caused by Genitive is its total high number of surnames in genitive in data. It would be interesting to find out the total number of all Finnish surnames' cases present; however, it falls out of scope of this research project.

The most interesting are errors appearing in surnames that are present in text in Nominative case, as supposedly those would be the easiest to translate, as they require no change whatsoever. It makes sense to take a closer look at these cases. Google translate made 5 errors translating surnames in Nominative case, and 3 out of those errors appear when translating *-iä* surnames, namely: *Pimiä* and *Hyypiä*. *Pimiä* is two times translated as *Pimi*, that could be explained as translation engine mistaking Nominative for Partitive and removing *-ä* to "create" Nominative. However, *Hyypiä* is translated into *Hyypä* which is harder to explain. The fourth mistake was made by translating *Pirinen* into *Pirine*. That again could be explained by translation engine removing a perceived Genitive ending *-n* to "make" a Nominative. The last mistake was skipping the surname all together.

Deep L made two errors when translating strings with surnames in Nominative case. First error appeared in the same string that Google Translate returned without a surname. Same happened with DeepL translation. Finnish "FREESTYLE : Pellinen aikalaskun ykkönen Ranskassa" was translated into: "FREESTYLE :

Sheet time number one in France” by Google Translate, and into: “FREESTYLE : Top of the time bill in France” by DeepL. The second error appeared when translating *Haaparanta* into *Haparanda*.

Discussion

The goal of this study was to analyze mistakes that machine translation engines make when translating Finnish surnames into English. In addition to that, I was trying to map out any possible error patterns that appear in translation. This project is meant to be seen as pilot research providing direction for any possible future studies. This being so, it was not in the scope of this project to analyze vast amount of data but to use digital tools to try and answer humanity related questions. As a result, outcomes of this study are not reliable to give any definitive answer to the research questions.

Even though, great deal of effort was taken into cleaning the data, during the analysis stage I noticed that some strings with content unrelated to the study were present. In addition to that, I have noticed several misspelled surnames in the source data. It is impossible to say how many more mistakes were not noticed by me.

Translating strings that have little to no shared context will no doubt affect the quality of translation output. Making a more reliable error analysis would require translating whole text and not separate strings. In addition to that, I translated the whole dataset at once with DeepL; however, I only managed to translate separate chunks of data with Google Translator. That possibly could have had a negative effect on quality of Google Translate output, as there was possibly even less possible context available.

Analysis shows some possible patterns, such as surnames ending with *-nen* containing most errors. In addition to that, surnames found in source text in Genitive case seem to cause most of the errors. However, with such a small dataset it is impossible to say is this because *-nen* surnames or genitive cases are overrepresented in source text. To get a more definitive answer, a bigger scale dataset needs to be used. In addition to that, analysis and comparison of all surnames, not only those with translation errors, need to be conducted.

Sources:

Maarit Koponen & Leena Salmi 2017. Post-editing quality: Analysing the correctness and necessity of post-editor corrections. *Linguistica Antverpiensia, New Series: Themes in Translation Studies* 16. S. 137–148 <https://lans-tts.uantwerpen.be/index.php/LANS-TTS/article/view/439/394>

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